

SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL FUNCTIONS IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. The modern education system serves a wide range of roles and responsibilities beyond academic knowledge. These functions include fostering social skills, emotional intelligence, ethical values, and promoting inclusivity and social justice. Inclusive education aims to provide equal opportunities for all students, creating an environment where diversity is celebrated and respected. Social-emotional learning focuses on developing students' emotional intelligence, empathy, and interpersonal skills. Schools also address social issues and promote social justice by engaging students in discussions and community service activities. Achieving these goals requires collaboration among teachers, administrators, parents, and the wider community. By embracing these functions, schools can effectively prepare students to become responsible and engaged citizens in today's complex world.

Keywords: Modern education system, roles and responsibilities, academic knowledge, social skills, emotional intelligence, ethical values, inclusivity, social justice, inclusive.

The socio-pedagogical functions in the modern education system encompass a wide range of roles and responsibilities that schools have in shaping students' social and educational development. These functions go beyond simply imparting academic knowledge and include fostering social skills, emotional intelligence, ethical values, and promoting inclusivity and social justice.

One of the key socio-pedagogical functions is inclusive education. Inclusive schools aim to provide equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds [4]. This involves creating an environment where diversity is celebrated and students learn to appreciate and respect differences. Inclusive education promotes a sense of belonging and social cohesion among students, preparing them to navigate a diverse and interconnected world.

Another important aspect of the socio-pedagogical function is social-emotional learning. This focuses on developing students' emotional intelligence, self-awareness, empathy, and interpersonal skills. By equipping students with these skills, schools enable them to manage their emotions, build positive relationships, and make responsible decisions. Social-emotional learning

enhances students' personal well-being and contributes to a harmonious and inclusive society [1].

Addressing social issues and promoting social justice is also a crucial socio-pedagogical function of schools. They provide a platform for students to learn about societal challenges such as poverty, inequality, discrimination, and environmental sustainability. By engaging students in discussions, projects, and community service activities, schools empower them to become active agents of change and contribute towards a more just and equitable society [2].

Achieving these socio-pedagogical goals requires collaboration among various stakeholders. Teachers play a central role in implementing effective pedagogical strategies and creating a supportive learning environment. Administrators provide the necessary resources and support systems to facilitate the socio-pedagogical function of schools. Parents are essential partners in their child's education, reinforcing the values taught at school and supporting their social and emotional development. The wider community also plays a crucial role by providing opportunities for students to engage with real-world issues and learn from diverse perspectives.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the modern education system serves a variety of roles and responsibilities beyond academic knowledge. It plays a crucial role in fostering social skills, emotional intelligence, ethical values, and promoting inclusivity and social justice. Inclusive education aims to provide equal opportunities for all students, creating an environment that celebrates and respects diversity. Social-emotional learning focuses on developing students' emotional intelligence, empathy, and interpersonal skills. Schools also address social issues and promote social justice through discussions and community service activities. Achieving these goals requires collaboration among teachers, administrators, parents, and the wider community. By embracing these functions, schools can effectively prepare students to become responsible and engaged citizens in today's complex world.

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